

Scienxt Journal of Microelectronics Engineering

Volume-2 // Issue-3 // Sept-Dec // Year-2024 // pp. 11-21

Optimizing energy distribution in hybrid electric vehicle: A fuzzy logic approach

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Abstract:

At present, transports are responsible for global carbon dioxide emissions and polluting the air in the atmosphere. This is considered to be a serious issue across the globe for transport systems. Moreover, these vehicular emissions contribute more to the carbonization process, which will be threatening to human survival in this world. Additionally, the weather forecasting suggests that there is going to be uncertainty over the weather predictions. That is why it is urgent to concentrate more on Renewable Energy Sources (RES), irrespective of the weather reports. So it is very important to select the proper Energy Management Systems (EMS), as it is vital to facilitate the use of RES. In this regard, Electric Vehicles (EVs) will be guaranteed to provide a cleaner and greener alternative measure of RES, but with a range of limitations. To overcome the restraints on the range and availability of RES, Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) will be a boon for EV users, and their EMS will be considered as cost-effective solutions for the proper EMS for the HEV. In order to improve the efficiency, energy consumption, and battery performance of the HEV, a suitable Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC)-based approach is to be proposed and designed in this paper.

Keywords:

Hybrid Electric Vehicles, PV-powered EVs, EMS in EVs, FLC-based HEV, Super capacitors

1. Introduction:

Experts contend that currently available oil reserves will be able to cover transportation needs, particularly for ground vehicles. Over the next 50 years, the global automobile capacity is anticipated to surge from 700 million vehicles to 2.5 billion vehicles. The inclusion of both environmental and financial concerns into contemporary automobile design is becoming increasingly significant. Many innovative technologies are being explored to replace combustion engines with electric gadgets. The inflexibility of the power system makes EVs currently unfeasible. One approach is to switch to HEV. The term "HEV" refers to vehicles that employ two or more energy sources to propel themselves. HEVs are widely suggested to maximize the fuel economy and reduce the emissions.

The merits of HEVs are enhancement of fuel sources and low emissions. Energy management procedures will be about to manage the efficiency HEV in all aspects of EMS. Researchers and scientists predict HEVs are to be an independent of fossil fuels and capable of being green technologies. However, there are significant technical and non-technical issues with establishing this battery, Super Capacitor (SC) etc. They would include societal perceptions, durability, refueling facilities protection and environmental sustainability cost, and so on. Another aspect is that researchers and manufacturers must examine, investigate, and test these vehicles before they are introduced to the road, which is considered a technical factor. The technical considerations would be the well-to-wheels productivity, which needs the execution of every part with maximum effectiveness in the system. Lithium-ion batteries now have a similar energy density to various kinds of battery packs while being considerably less expensive. The research presented here attempts to boost the State-of-Charge (SoC) profile of HEVs, enabling them to travel more kilometers in electric mode.

The improved SOC profile with a smoother time domain curve leads to efficient energy transfer and improved battery performance. Controllers that use fuzzy logic have been employed to accomplish this. However, the electrification of transportation presents here more challenges. The primary issue lies in creating an efficient energy management strategy for HEVs. At the moment, HEVs have a considerably limited range. Currently, EVs can only drive for a range of about 155–205 km on a single charge, which is insufficient for long-term sustainability. HEV technology has major obstacles due to battery size, quantity, and

ergonomics. Efficient EMS is crucial for increasing the range of HEVs. To achieve this, it is mandatory to improve the battery's SoC profile. The state of charge (SOC) of a battery is stated as a percentage of the battery's potential. A better SOC profile will help us suggest the efficient use of electricity.

It is feasible to use them as the principal storage of energy components in automobile applications. However, lithium-ion batteries have demerits such as low power density and short cycle life. A hybrid energy storage system (HESS) for EVs could involve using ultra capacitors (UC) in addition to batteries. This UC is also called SC. This SC will be effectively used to capture the energy during regenerative braking in automobile applications. It can be tolerable to capture the energy at a very high surge voltage. As we know, while UCs offers high power density, long cycle life, and quick dynamic output, they have a lower energy density than batteries. Together, they are expected to complement each other.

2. Dynamics of hybrid e-vehicles:

The diagram below represents the block diagram of the HEV. In this approach, EMS is to be incorporated with solar panel output and super capacitor output, which will help boost the performance of the battery in terms of its added mileage and so on. Nowadays, there are numerous hybrid-optional EVs coming onto the market. The sales are also increasing due to certain features in the range coverage, such as solar-powered options and capturing regenerative braking energy during the deceleration of the EV. That is why it is going to be liked by the customers. The batter is getting sufficient energy from all the RES. Real-time EMS is an added advantage for the HEV. A fuzzy logic-based controller is implemented in the HEV to harness sufficient energy from the available integrated RES in the HEV in an optimal way.

Figure. 1: HEV dynamics

That is why we have chosen this fuzzy logic-based implantation strategy to retain optimal energy in the battery for optimal performance in terms of the SOC of the battery. SoC plays a vital role in the case of HEV, which will be heavily influenced by the optimization of the proper fuzzy logic technology. Here in this passage, it is highlighted that the feature is to harness more energy from the RES for optimal performance.

2.1. Energy storage system for HEV:

Batteries, PV arrays, and SCs are going to constitute the EMS, which is only going to be used in our HEV. These devices will serve as electrochemical storage but have distinct features that will be contrary to one another in a HESS. This is due to the fact that batteries have high energy density but low power density, allowing them to store a large amount of energy while slowly dissipating it.

The SCs, on the other hand, have high power, allowing them to discharge energy quickly. In a hybrid electric vehicle with varying operable conditions, speed, and necessary power, the combination of battery, solar panel energy, and a SC would allow the battery's lifetime to be extended because the energy during transient or peak demand could be met from auxiliary sources such as the SC and PV array. So the auxiliary sources will support this HESS effectively when there is a huge power demand in the EMS of the EV.

2.2. Super capacitor for HEV

One technology for storing energy that has been altered to resemble capacitors is the SC but it ultimately has extraordinarily high capacitance and durability as compared with conventional capacitors. Electric double-layer capacitors (ELDC), pseudo-capacitors, and hybrid capacitors

are the three types of SCs normally utilized in EVs that are known to everyone. However, the most widely utilized SC in HEV is ELDC since it has the highest power density (about 1.2–3.6 kW/kg) and the smallest energy density (about 5.5-7.28 Wh/kg) among all three super capacitors.

Additionally, it is noticed that the energy that has been conserved in an SC is going to be found to be in proportion to the square of its voltage potential. If a capacitor reaches 0.52 from 1, the measured level of 74.75% of the conserved energy is in the condition to be dissipated out. Lastly, a capacitor is considered to be fully discharged when it is declined to 0.45 from 1, and the 50.56 percent of the expected nominal voltage is noted here as the cut-off voltage of an SC.

2.3. Battery for HEV:

The point to be considered here is that the proper selection of right battery for a HEV is a little bit complicated task even as it is available in market today with lot of varieties. Batteries are constrained with the proper weighing of the terms by Ah capacity, power density, efficacy, and durability of cycles in the transportation sector. Lead-acid batteries are commonly utilized in lightweight EVs due to their low cost even though their disposal is a biggest challenge. Eco-friendly batteries, such as nickel-metal hydrides, are already being used in EVs, although they require a complex charging algorithm and have the longest charging times.

The HESS consists of a lithium-ion battery model that includes a DC voltage source, a series resistor, and two extra resistor/capacitor pairs (R1/C1 and R2/C2). These elements' values are defined in the order of polynomial functions, similar to the battery's state of charge as listed below. For example:

$$R_s, battery(SOC) = 0.015 - 0.2345SOC - 1.69SOC^2 - 5.68SOC^3 + 9.56SOC^4 - 8.236SOC^5 + 2.568SOC^6, \text{ Optimal DC Voltage source } (SOC) = 2.584 + 14.986SOC - 100.01SOC^2 + 296.245SOC^3 - 444.565SOC^4 - 330.89SOC^5 - 96.121SOC^6$$

3. Fuzzy model for controlling the HEV:

There have been numerous studies conducted on the topic of fuzzy logic controllers for HEV EMS. There appears to be a high level of relevance because it identifies the condition in which the particular method stated matters most significantly. What we anticipate giving it flexibility and making it similar to human decision-making is the capacity to predict the outcome depending on a situation. It works by using lingual 'if...then' markers and then taking into consideration the ambiguity of the stipulations, which usually arise only when we determine the outcome. FLC is considered a highly valuable controller, and it is widely used across the globe. In this design, a FLC is to serve as the EMS for a HEV.

To implement the fuzzy-based logic controller, the prescribed stages must be followed to get the HEV controlled in all aspects of its driving consideration as well as battery SOC specifications. They are actually three stages of control through FLC that are to be followed as they are. They are fuzzification, inference, and defuzzification. Fuzzification is defined as a way of activating fuzzy sets with clearly defined inputs and outcomes, as well as the function of membership. Inference is an operation in which established guidelines evolve based on input and output variables.

Figure. 2: Fuzzy logic basic structure

A few of the fuzzy rules employed in this FLC are shown in Table. 1. Defuzzification is the process of creating a single, crisp image to display the fuzzy sets.

Table. 1:

Fuzzy rules	
1	If (dc_r is pos_L), then (Pbat is neg_L), (Psc is zero), and (0.9)

2	If (dc_r is pos_S), then (Pbat is neg_S), (Psc is zero), and (0.56)
3	If (dc_r is zero), then (Pbat is zero), (Psc is zero), and (1.1)
4	If (dc_r is neg_S) and (Sc is not over), then (Pbat is zero) and (Psc is pos_S) (1.2).
5	If (dc_r is neg_L) and (Sc is not over), then (Pbat is zero) (Psc is pos_L) (1.1).
6	If (dc_r is neg_S) and (Sc is over), then (Pbat is pos_S), (Psc is zero), and (0.58)
7	If (dc_r is neg_L) and (Sc is over), then (Pbat is pos_L)(Psc is zero)(1.2).
8	If (P_load is large) and (Sc is not under), then (Pbat is zero) (Psc is neg_L) (1.12).
9	If (P_load is small) and (speed is high) and (Sc is not under) and (slope is not up), then (Pbat is zero) (Psc is neg_S) (0.253).
10	If (P_load is neg-zero) and (speed is low) and (Sc is not under) and (slope is not up), then (Pbat is zero) (Psc is neg_S) (0.056)

Table. 1 above lists the information for the basic input and the output variables. The rules are definitely for the output voltage, load power, maximum speed, and voltage of the super capacitor that is simulated up to a maximum voltage as mentioned above. These are the measured data that are to be applied and incorporated as per the constraints when it is simulated into the simulator in MATLAB.

Figure. 3: Model of a FLC for HEV

4. Results:

The below results are the simulation results for battery and super capacitor current. In view of EMS in HEV, it is very much important to have a proper energy feed between one another to have a better power distribution among all the components. From the results it can be well understood that the positive results are showing highly expected output from both super capacitor as well PV modules to have a better power management based on the power demand incurred during the available 24 hours power demand.

Figure. 4: Battery current

Figure. 5: Super capacitor current

From the results, it has been noticed that the voltage of the SC dropped only a few tens of volts from 469.4 to 350 volts. The better the performance of the SC, the better the EMS. During charging and discharging time, the SC has satisfactorily maintained the constant voltage throughout the electrochemical charging and discharging continual processes for about 400 seconds.

5. Conclusion:

Thus, the FLC for the EMS of the HEV has been experimentally found to be the best and possible solution for the customers who are keen on using the EV for all their transportation purposes economically by using the combination of PV array, SC, and battery. This combination adds extra energy for the battery in times of poor sunlight irradiance and so on. Because it has been experimentally proven that solar energy can be harnessed for about 4.5 hours per day. At this time, only the availability of sunlight is at its peak to retrieve all of its energy. So EV owners cannot depend only on the RES, such as sunlight, in this case. That is why we used SC and got better results in terms of its performance when it is combined to supply its energy to the battery to be stored. One of the important concepts attached to this paper is the fuzzy logic implementation, which has shown a certain ability to manage the uncertainties in the data for practical EV applications. Furthermore, it provided a way for future experimental findings in the field of vehicular transportation in terms of its EMS.

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